

EXPLORING THE INTERSECTION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING (CALL) AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE ANXIETY: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

This paper delves into the multifaceted realm of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) and its intricate relationship with Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA). Beginning with a definition of CALL and a historical overview of its evolution in English language education, the paper then examines the theoretical foundations shaping CALL methodologies. Subsequently, it delves into the significant role of FLA in language learning contexts, highlighting its impact on learners' motivation, engagement, and language acquisition outcomes. Drawing from previous studies, the paper explores the intricate interplay between CALL interventions and FLA levels, shedding light on both the potential benefits and challenges associated with technology integration in language learning environments. Finally, the paper offers recommendations for educators and policymakers to effectively harness CALL tools while addressing FLA concerns, aiming to create supportive and conducive learning environments for language learners.

Keywords: computer-assisted language learning (CALL), foreign language anxiety (FLA), language proficiency, teacher training

1. Introduction

In today's globalised world, the ability to communicate in multiple languages is increasingly recognized as a valuable skill. As a result, language learning has become a significant focus in both educational and professional settings. With advancements in technology, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) has emerged as a promising tool to enhance language acquisition and proficiency. However, alongside the benefits of CALL, researchers and educators have also noted the prevalence of foreign language anxiety (FLA) among language learners.

Foreign language anxiety, characterised by feelings of apprehension or nervousness when learning or using a second or foreign language, has been widely documented in language learning literature. It can manifest in various forms, such as fear of making mistakes, anxiety about speaking in front of others, or discomfort in unfamiliar linguistic environments. FLA not only hampers language learners' performance but also affects their motivation and willingness to engage in the target language.

Given the growing prominence of both CALL and FLA in language education, there is a pressing need to understand how these two phenomena intersect and influence each other. While CALL holds the potential to alleviate some aspects of FLA through its interactive and personalised learning experiences, it may also exacerbate anxiety in certain contexts, such as technical challenges or social comparison with peers.

This comprehensive review aims to explore the intersection of CALL and FLA, synthesising existing research to provide insights into the complex relationship between technology-enhanced language learning and learners' affective states. By examining the strengths, limitations, and potential synergies between CALL and FLA, this review seeks to inform educators, researchers, and practitioners about effective strategies for promoting positive language learning experiences and addressing the challenges posed by FLA in technology-mediated environments. Many articles on this topic

conclude that there is a need for a wide sample of participants and the need to test different levels of language proficiency. In addition, the research gap shows that such a topic has never been explored in Kazakhstan.

2. Definition of CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning)

Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) refers to the integration of computer technology in language learning and teaching processes to enhance language acquisition and proficiency. CALL encompasses a wide range of applications, software, and digital resources designed to facilitate language learning activities, including vocabulary drills, grammar exercises, multimedia presentations, interactive simulations, and virtual language labs. It leverages the capabilities of computers and digital devices to provide learners with interactive and personalised learning experiences, allowing them to practise language skills in a variety of contexts and formats.

3. History of Using CALL in English Language Class

The integration of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) into English language classes has a rich history that spans several decades. Initially, emerging in the mid-20th century, CALL has undergone significant developments and transformations, shaping the landscape of English language education.

Early efforts to incorporate technology into English language instruction can be traced back to the 1960s and 1970s. During this period, pioneers such as Donald G. Perrin explored the potential of computers in language learning, leading to the development of innovative programs like the PLATO system (Perrin, 1977). These early endeavours laid the groundwork for subsequent advancements in CALL methodologies and technologies.

The 1980s witnessed a surge of interest in CALL within English language classrooms, driven by the increasing availability of personal computers and educational software. Researchers like Warschauer (1996) conducted seminal studies examining the effectiveness

of CALL programs in enhancing English language proficiency among learners. This era saw the emergence of interactive language learning software, multimedia resources, and computer-mediated communication tools, offering learners new avenues for practising and improving their English language skills.

The advent of the internet in the 1990s ushered in a new era of CALL, characterised by the development of online language learning platforms, virtual classrooms, and digital resources accessible to English language learners worldwide. The integration of multimedia, web-based applications, and social media further expanded the possibilities for interactive and collaborative language learning experiences in English language classes.

In the 21st century, the rapid evolution of CALL continues to shape English language education. Advances in artificial intelligence, mobile technology, and adaptive learning platforms have revolutionised the way English is taught and learned, with a growing emphasis on personalised and immersive learning experiences tailored to individual learner needs.

As CALL continues to evolve, English language educators remain at the forefront of exploring innovative pedagogical approaches and integrating cutting-edge technologies to enhance the teaching and learning of English as a second or foreign language.

4. Theoretical Foundations of CALL

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is grounded in various theoretical frameworks, each influencing the design and implementation of CALL programs in English language education. Behaviorism, as one of the earliest theoretical perspectives, emphasises the role of reinforcement and conditioning in learning (Skinner, 1958). In the context of CALL, behaviourist principles are evident in drill-and-practice software, where learners receive immediate feedback and reinforcement for correct responses (Chapelle, 2001).

Contrastingly, constructivism posits that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction with the learning environment (Vygotsky, 1978). CALL applications informed by constructivist theory often incorporate collaborative tasks and authentic language use, aligning with communicative language teaching (CLT) principles (Warschauer & Kern, 2000). These programs encourage learner autonomy and engagement through meaningful interactions in virtual environments (Meskill & Anthony, 2010).

Sociocultural theory, drawing from the work of Vygotsky, emphasises the role of social interaction and cultural context in learning (Lantolf & Thorne, 2006). In CALL, sociocultural perspectives underscore the importance of collaborative learning spaces and the integration of authentic materials and contexts (Stockwell, 2017). Virtual reality simulations and online communities facilitate situated learning experiences, allowing learners to engage with language in culturally relevant contexts (Godwin-Jones, 2018).

5. Previous Studies on the Relationship Between CALL and Foreign Language Anxiety

Language learning anxiety refers to the feelings of apprehension, tension, or nervousness experienced by individuals in language learning contexts, which can

impede their ability to acquire, retain, or effectively use a second or foreign language (Horwitz et al., 1986). Language learning anxiety can arise from various sources, such as performance pressure, social factors, fear of failure, or perceived language inadequacy. It may manifest in different language learning contexts, including classrooms, language labs, study abroad programs, or social interactions with native speakers. The significance of language learning anxiety in language education cannot be overstated. It profoundly impacts learners' motivation, engagement, and language learning outcomes. High levels of anxiety can hinder learners' willingness to communicate, negatively impacting their language development and overall learning outcomes (Phillips, 1992). Understanding and addressing language learning anxiety is crucial for creating supportive and effective learning environments that promote learners' well-being and success in language acquisition (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014).

The relationship between CALL and FLA (foreign language anxiety) has been investigated in several studies, offering valuable insights into the impact of technology on learners' emotional experiences and language learning outcomes. For instance, Lisnychenko et al. (2021) examined the impact of transitioning from traditional classrooms to distance learning on students' foreign language anxiety, revealing a general tendency for anxiety levels to increase as a result of changes in the learning environment and the nature of distance learning. Factors contributing to this heightened anxiety included the lack of personal contact, Zoom fatigue, and deadlines. Despite these challenges, the study found mixed responses among students: while some reported experiencing less pressure and anxiety in distance learning due to increased flexibility and autonomy, others expressed heightened anxiety and decreased motivation towards English classes. Various types of foreign language anxiety were identified, including communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, fear of making mistakes, and test anxiety. Communication apprehension notably increased, characterised by nervousness when speaking spontaneously and fear of speaking in front of the class, exacerbated by the lack of verbal support and prompts from teachers and peers. Additionally, distance learning intensified students' fear of negative evaluation, as limited feedback contributed to feelings of insecurity and uncertainty. Interestingly, the fear of making mistakes decreased in distance learning settings, possibly due to reduced control and formal assessment from teachers. Furthermore, test anxiety levels slightly decreased during the transition to distance learning, potentially attributed to increased test-taking practice and focused preparation. Similarly to the article by Lisnychenko et al. (2021), the results of some research studies by Ahangari (2014) and Mehdi et al. (2022) found that some techniques, exercises or other types of preparation can reduce test or exercise anxiety in studying a foreign language. The effectiveness of various technology-integrated language learning approaches is explored across several studies. Ahangari (2014) investigates the impact of computer-assisted cooperative language learn-

ing (CALL) on reading comprehension and foreign language anxiety among Iranian high school students. The study reveals a significant improvement in reading comprehension and a reduction in anxiety levels among students exposed to cooperative learning integrated into CALL, highlighting the benefits of integrating cooperative activities into computer-assisted learning settings. As mentioned before, similar findings are echoed by Nasri et al. (2022), who demonstrate that CALL-based instruction leads to enhanced speaking complexity, accuracy, and fluency, along with a reduction in foreign language speaking anxiety among EFL learners. Both studies emphasise the importance of incorporating technology in language education to improve learning outcomes and alleviate anxiety.

Furthermore, Randall (2019) surveyed the landscape of robot-assisted language learning (RALL), highlighting the potential benefits of robotic technologies in reducing anxiety and enhancing engagement among language learners. The study identified key features of robots, such as naturalistic voices and personalised interactions, that contribute to learners' emotional well-being and language learning progress. Moreover, Javanbakht and Hadian (2014) investigated the effects of test anxiety on Iranian EFL learners' reading test performance, revealing no significant correlation between foreign language reading anxiety and reading comprehension scores. The study suggested that while test anxiety may influence learners' emotional experiences, its impact on language proficiency may vary depending on individual and contextual factors. Liu and Xiangming (2019) explored changes in and effects of FLA on postgraduate students' English test performance, highlighting the significance of addressing anxiety in language learning contexts to promote positive learning outcomes. The study underscored the importance of creating supportive learning environments and implementing effective anxiety management strategies to enhance language learning experiences and outcomes. Furthermore, Aljameel (2022) reviewed research efforts on CALL in Saudi Arabian EFL classrooms, emphasising the importance of addressing barriers to technology integration and providing adequate training and support for educators. The study highlighted the potential of technology-enhanced language learning methods in promoting language proficiency and fostering positive affective states among learners, thereby contributing to the advancement of EFL education in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, Alias and Noor Rashid (2018) examined the correlation between students' language learning anxiety and language proficiency among Civil Engineering students in Malaysian polytechnics, revealing a significant negative correlation between test anxiety and language proficiency. The study underscored the importance of addressing anxiety in language learning environments and implementing effective teaching strategies to mitigate its impact on learners' language learning outcomes. The role of teachers in reducing language anxiety and their training in this aspect are crucial components in fostering effective language learning environments. Research underscores the necessity for teacher training and support in integrating technology, particularly Computer-Assisted

Language Learning (CALL), into language classrooms (Aljameel, 2022). While studies reveal the potential of technology to enhance language learning, challenges such as inadequate training and resources hinder its effective integration (Aljameel, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of online teaching methods, highlighting the importance of continuous professional development for educators in educational technology (Learning from Experience in the Midst of COVID-19). Experienced online instructors possess advantages over novices, emphasising the need for training programs that address varying levels of online teaching experience (Learning from Experience in the Midst of COVID-19). Furthermore, incorporating CALL into language learning environments has shown significant benefits, including reducing Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety (FLSA) and improving speaking complexity, accuracy, and fluency (Nasri et al., 2022). CALL creates a supportive and motivating learning environment by reducing anxiety through non-threatening communication and learner-teacher rapport (Nasri et al., 2022). However, addressing anxiety in language classrooms extends beyond technology integration. Studies highlight the negative correlation between test anxiety and language proficiency, emphasising the importance of creating a less threatening classroom environment and encouraging enjoyable learning experiences (Alias & Noor Rashid, 2018). Thus, teacher training programs should encompass strategies for creating supportive learning environments, addressing anxiety triggers, and promoting positive attitudes towards language learning (Alias & Noor Rashid, 2018). Overall, teachers play a pivotal role in reducing language anxiety, and their training in implementing effective strategies is essential for fostering successful language learning experiences.

6. Discussions about the Evolution, Impact, and Future Directions of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL)

The burgeoning field of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) offers a rich tapestry of insights into the integration of technology in language education. CALL encompasses a diverse array of applications, software, and digital resources designed to augment language acquisition and proficiency. Over the decades, CALL has evolved significantly, paralleling advancements in technology and pedagogical theory.

Historically, CALL has witnessed remarkable growth, from the pioneering efforts of individuals like Donald G. Perrin to the widespread adoption of online platforms and virtual classrooms in the 21st century. Theoretical frameworks such as behaviourism, constructivism, and sociocultural theory have underpinned the development and implementation of CALL programs, offering diverse perspectives on language learning and pedagogy.

Moreover, previous studies have shed light on the intricate relationship between CALL and Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA), elucidating how technology can both exacerbate and alleviate learners' emotional experiences. While CALL-based interventions have shown

promise in reducing FLA and enhancing language proficiency, challenges persist, including issues of authenticity, technical barriers, and student perceptions.

Future research directions in this domain hold immense promise. There is a pressing need to explore innovative pedagogical approaches that leverage technology to mitigate language anxiety and foster optimal learning outcomes. Additionally, examining the effectiveness of various CALL interventions across diverse learner populations and contexts can provide valuable insights into the best practices and instructional strategies.

7. Recommendations for Addressing Foreign Language Anxiety in Language Learning Environments

1. Teacher Training and Support:

- Provide teachers with training and support in integrating technology effectively into language learning environments, especially in the distance learning contexts. This includes training on using communication tools, providing effective feedback, and creating a supportive online atmosphere.

2. Promotion of Effective Communication Strategies:

- Emphasise the teaching of effective communication strategies to help students overcome anxiety related to speaking in front of others or making mistakes. This can include techniques for managing communication apprehension and fear of negative evaluation.

3. Encouragement of Autonomy and Self-Evaluation:

- Encourage autonomy and self-evaluation among language learners to promote a sense of control over their learning process. This can help reduce anxiety by allowing students to set their own learning goals and pace.

4. Changing Attitudes Towards Mistakes:

- Foster a positive attitude towards mistakes as part of the learning process. Encourage students to view mistakes as opportunities for growth and learning rather than sources of anxiety.

5. Integration of Cooperative Learning:

- Incorporate cooperative learning activities into computer-assisted language learning settings. Research suggests that cooperative learning can enhance learning outcomes and reduce language anxiety by promoting peer support and collaboration.

6. Creation of Supportive Learning Environments:

- Create supportive learning environments that minimise anxiety triggers and provide opportunities for students to practise language skills in a low-stakes setting. This can include providing regular feedback, fostering a sense of community, and offering resources for managing anxiety.

7. Continuous Professional Development:

- Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for educators to stay updated on the best practices in language teaching, including strategies for addressing language anxiety in both traditional and technology-enhanced environments.

8. Further Research and Investigation:

- Encourage further research to explore the complex relationship between FLA and CALL, especially

in different cultural and educational contexts. This can help identify effective strategies for mitigating anxiety and enhancing language learning outcomes.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, this comprehensive review delves into the intersection of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) and Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA), shedding light on their complex relationship and implications for language education. The paper traces the historical evolution of CALL in English language education, highlighting its transformative impact on language learning methodologies over the decades. It explores the theoretical foundations shaping CALL interventions, including behaviourism, constructivism, and sociocultural theory, and their implications for language pedagogy.

Furthermore, the review synthesises findings from previous studies on FLA and CALL, elucidating how technology can both exacerbate and alleviate learners' anxiety in language learning contexts. While CALL interventions have shown promise in reducing FLA and enhancing language proficiency, challenges such as authenticity, technical barriers, and student perceptions persist.

The review culminates in a set of recommendations aimed at informing educators, policymakers, and researchers about effective strategies for promoting positive language learning experiences and addressing FLA concerns. These recommendations include providing teacher training and support in technology integration, promoting effective communication strategies, encouraging learner autonomy, changing attitudes towards mistakes, integrating cooperative learning activities, creating supportive learning environments, and advocating for continuous professional development.

Overall, the review underscores the importance of ongoing research and investigation into the complex interplay between FLA and CALL, especially in diverse cultural and educational contexts. By addressing these issues and implementing evidence-based strategies, educators can create more supportive and conducive learning environments for language learners, ultimately fostering their success and proficiency in target languages.

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